

CULTURAL LIFE IN CENTRAL ASIA IN THE 16TH–17TH CENTURIES

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Abstract. The following scientific article discusses the historical situation and development of cultural life in Central Asia in the 16th-17th centuries, its manifestations, and connections. The stages of development of culture in Central Asia during the khanates after the Timurid state and its place in world culture are unique. The successes behind the rise of culture during the reign of Abdullah Khan II are especially noteworthy.

Keywords: centralized state, Samarkand paper, copper vessels, cotton, silk, poets, domes.

Introduction

In the 16th–17th centuries, the historical situation in Central Asia was extremely complex from socio-political and economic perspectives. This period was characterized by the unstable existence of the Central Asian khanates, numerous large-scale military conflicts, and persistent economic difficulties. By the beginning of the 16th century, the once-powerful Timurid state began to experience a profound decline.

The main reasons for this crisis were feudal fragmentation and intense struggles for political power, which significantly weakened the political authority of the Timurid dynasty and created conditions that enabled the conquest of the country by the Shaybanid forces. In this process, conflicts and tensions between feudal lords and the peasantry also played an important role.

Taking full advantage of this situation, the forces of Shaybani Khan succeeded within a short period in conquering a vast state stretching from the Syr Darya River to Central Afghanistan. Already at the beginning of the 16th century, the extensive territories of Mawarannahr and Khorasan came under the control of Muhammad Shaybani. As a result, the once-powerful Timurid state was completely dismantled. During the reign of Abdullah Khan, the Bukhara Khanate succeeded in

reclaiming and even expanding the territories that had been lost during the period of Shaybani Khan. The khanate brought under its control vast regions of Mawarannahr, including Balkh (1573), Samarkand (1578), Tashkent (1582), Fergana (1583), Badakhshan (1584), Kulob (1585), Khorasan (1588), and Khwarazm (1595–1596), thereby emerging as a powerful military state.

In 1582, Abdullah Khan carried out a series of major military campaigns, subjugating important urban centers such as Tashkent, Samarkand, Shahrisabz, Hisor, and Qarshi.

In 1583, he officially proclaimed himself khan. “...he devoted considerable effort to internal state affairs—introducing the minting of coins and regulating their circulation, standardizing conditions for domestic and foreign trade, and overseeing the construction of irrigation canals during his reign. Abdullah Khan succeeded in subordinating the governors of distant provinces to centralized state authority, which led to a significant strengthening of the country’s economic condition” [1]

Main Part

Abdullah Khan’s significant contribution to the development of the state can be seen in the large-scale construction projects he carried out in the interests of the population. In 1583, the khan ordered the construction of the Aqchopsay dam and reservoir near the village of Eski Oqchop, on the northern slopes of the Nurata Mountains. The remains of this structure have been preserved to this day.

In addition, he initiated the construction of water-distribution facilities such as Puli Karmana, Puli Mehtar Qasim, and Puli Chahorminor on the Zarafshan River, as well as numerous irrigation canals branching from the Vakhsh River. These projects provided substantial benefits for the population engaged in agriculture.

According to the records of the qadi of Samarkand, more than 60 different types of crafts existed in Samarkand in the 16th century.

Historical sources indicate that, in order to strengthen his state, Abdullah Khan ordered the reconstruction of the Bukhara city wall, after which the Joybor area, located to the southwest of Bukhara, was incorporated into the city by royal decree. This area included the neighborhoods of Joyizor, Chakar, Dastorbandon, and Jafaron. Within the quarter, a madrasa, mosque, sardoba (water reservoir), and a pool were constructed. Until the 1920s, this area was inhabited by wealthy families of Bukhara.

As the ancestors of the Joybor Khoja were buried in the Chor Bakr cemetery in Bukhara, a magnificent mausoleum was constructed there in the 16th century, and the site became an important place of pilgrimage. However, in the political circumstances that emerged in the country during the first half of the 17th century,

the Joybor Khoja lost his former influence and status.

The name of Abdullah Khan is still praised as the one who established order and culture in Turkestan. All public buildings are attributed to him: the laying of new canals, the construction of caravanserais in the steppe, etc. [2] After the death of Abdullah Khan, his state collapsed. Bukhara, an important strategic center of the centralized state, passed to a new dynasty. Under its rule, only a part of the state founded by Abdullah Khan remained. The centralized state of the Shaybanids, which they had created by conquering other states, fighting them, and expanding and strengthening religion, began to flourish. In this, due to the unification of feudal princes, regions, and economic development, only large feudal lords and religious leaders benefited. The common people were severely oppressed and began to live in hardship. The richest, most productive lands were in the hands of large landowners. They controlled the entire economy and occupied the most visible positions in public life. Religious leaders were also not without the favor of the khan.

By the end of the 16th century, power in Transoxiana passed from the Shaybanid dynasty to the Ashtarkhanid dynasty. Imamqulikhan (1611-1642), who came to the helm of the state, tried to strengthen the state. He annexed many provinces. The situation in the country improved somewhat. Life in Bukhara returned to normal.

“During the rule of the Ashtarkhanids, as well as Shaybanid Abdullahkhan, an extensive and well-organized central administrative apparatus was formed in the Bukhara Khanate. Although its system was inherited from the Timurid era, it houses, mosques, mausoleums, madrasas, sometimes bridges, wells, etc.” [4] underwent significant changes depending on the real conditions under the Uzbek khans” [3].

At that time, the issue of endowment became one of the most important issues. “The concept of endowment is any useful object, land, mills, baths, markets, shops, canals, slaves, money, etc., which is mainly officially given to charitable organizations, and the funds received from these organizations are spent on during the reign of these khans, various constructions and irrigation systems that had been destroyed in wars were renovated. Great attention was paid to the development of agriculture. Great attention was paid to the Zarafshan River flowing through the territory of Samarkand, and a water distributor was built in 1502. The river was one of the main sources of agriculture.

In the 16th century, in the cities of Central Asia, such crafts as weaving, pottery, metalworking, the production of writing paper, construction, clothing, and food were developed. Among these, cotton and cotton processing, the production of

cotton and silk fabrics, and their polishing occupied a special place. Textile products were especially popular in the Middle East. The fabrics woven mainly in the village of Zandana were of high quality.

In the 16th and 17th centuries, the art of carving wood, stone, and bronze flourished in cities. One of the most famous craftsmen of that era was Master Kamol, who was famous for his artistic polishing of iron utensils. His utensils and objects were widely distributed among the wealthy.

There is also information about the use of firearms in Central Asia in the first half of the 16th century. Copper objects were very delicate. In general, the cities of Central Asia were famous for tanning leather and making fabrics, for their beauty, brilliance, and craftsmanship, and were appreciated in the Moscow state and Siberia.

In Central Asia, handicrafts reached a high point of development in the 16th and 17th centuries, as evidenced by the surviving clay, iron vessels, paper, weapons, fabrics, and wooden objects.

In these centuries, we can see the great strides made by the art of book publishing. "At the beginning of the century, among those who fled from Herat to Central Asia, there were also masters of artistic book decoration. Some went alone, sometimes a whole caravan was formed. This happened in the spring of 1512. About five hundred people set off for Transoxiana. This happened later, in the 20s and 30s of the 16th century. These caravans included prominent priests, poets, musicians, singers, and reciters, among whom were artistic manuscript writers-calligraphers, goldsmiths, and miniaturists" [5].

The quality of the writing paper produced during the period under study was not inferior to that of China. Samarkand writing paper was also famous abroad, and its production continued for a thousand years. It did not lose its popularity even in the 16th century [6].

The spread of paper developed internal and external trade. In this regard, Samarkand was one of the oldest trading centers of the East. Trade routes to various countries passed through it, and caravans regularly traveled. The bazaars were expanded and architecturally renovated. Abdullah Khan built square domes at the intersections of trade routes. Caravans also traded with the Far East through Maverannahr.

Central Asia, starting from the second half of the 16th century, expanded its trade relations with neighboring countries. "Every year in the city of Bukhara there was a gathering of merchants who came in large caravans from India, Iran, Balkh, Russia and other neighboring countries," wrote the English traveler Jenkinson [8].

Tashkent, Samarkand and the capital Bukhara gathered prominent

entrepreneurs, merchants, cultural figures, musicians, and poets of Central Asia. In the 16th century, there were some freedoms compared to the 15th century. Literature, historical sciences, urban planning, and fine arts developed. Poetry rose to a high level.

By this time, Bukhara had become one of the centers of Islam. The palaces of Abdulaziz Khan and Abdullah Khan also had a library with a collection of rare books with artistic decorations. Skilled calligraphers and miniaturists worked in this palace, copying and decorating manuscripts, literary, historical and other works.

During those times, the collections of poetry of Hasankhoja Nisari "Muzakkir al-ahbob" (1566), Mutribi's "Tazkirat al-shuaro" (1604-1605), Muhammad Salih's "Shayboninoma", Abdullah ibn Muhammad's "Zubdat-ul-asror", Hafiz Tanish Bukhari's "Abdullanoma", Zainiddin Vasifi's "Bada'e' ul-vaqo'e" were created. Sharafiddin Ali Yazdi's "Zafarnoma", Rashiduddin Fazlulloh's "Jami' at-tawarikh" and a number of other works were translated into the Uzbek language. Shaybonikhan, Mir Arab, Abdullahkhan, Kukaldash, and Muhammad Sharif madrasas were built. Attention was paid to education. Schools were opened in every mahalla. Admission to schools began at the age of 6. It left a deep mark on Central Asian literature. These works gave historians the names of literary figures who lived and created at that time. This, in turn, shows that our people who lived in the 16th century were rich in literature and culture. Even merchants, artisans, and ordinary people would gather together and hold sherkhan evenings. Even today, this tradition has been preserved among people of various professions in the Fergana oasis. Our people are especially fond of poetry, participating in various contests and competitions, expressing their love for poetry.

By the second half of the 16th century, there were about 300 literary poets in Bukhara alone. Of these, Abdurakhmon Mushfiqi, who came from a craftsman's background, left behind three poetic divans. Mushfiqi was one of the most prominent court poets of the 16th century. He worked at the court of Abdullah Khan, writing poems praising the khans.

At this point, it is worth mentioning another poet, Binoi. Binoi was from Herat and wrote poems in Persian in Bukhara praising the khans. His pen includes poems praising the heroism and conquests of Shaibani Khans. Along with poets, one should not forget the historians of that time.

Among them is Hafiz Tanish, whom our historians have always looked at with interest. His work "Abdulla-noma" is still useful to historians and researchers of Uzbekistan. During this period, after A. Navoi, historical and literary works began to be created in the Uzbek language. Muhammad Salih's work "Shaibani-noma" is

one of them. The work of medieval literature “Babur-noma” was widely distributed among the people. The historical work “Zubdat al-asar” by Abdullo ibn Muhammad reveals the reasons for the death of Shaibani Khan. Of course, it would be a mistake to limit ourselves to these works. There are hundreds of unexplored works in the book and manuscript funds of our republic.

Conclusion

To summarize, in the 16th-17th centuries, the role of madrasahs in the formation of national culture was unparalleled. If we look at history, from the Shaybani Khans to the Ashtar Khans, they tried to build many madrasahs and mosques, relying on the clergy, thereby raising the cultural level of the people.

During these periods, along with literature and poetry, musicology also began to develop. This was especially noticeable in Samarkand and Bukhara. Among the musical instruments, national musical instruments such as the trumpet, trumpet, rubab, chang, kamancha, dutar, setor became widespread. Poets, along with writing poetry, also performed their poems as songs. This gave impetus to the development of musical art in Central Asia. Among the poet-musicians, the names of such master artists as Hasan Kavkabi, Mawlana Riza, Pirmuhammad Kulol were prominent. "Many poets were excellent musicians. A whole work on the history of music was prepared by the Bukhara Mowlavi Kavkabi» [7].

Of course, the cultural and educational life of society in the 16th-17th centuries cannot be compared with the achievements of science and technology in the 19th-20th centuries in Central Asia during the First Renaissance and the Second Renaissance in the 14th-15th centuries. However, the people of the period we are studying continued it, using the wealth of previous centuries. Despite the collapse of the feudal system, cultural and social life and science in Central Asia did not stop. As V.V. Barthold affirmed, "... the successful continuation of ancient cultural traditions was reflected in various literary works, which, although not within the framework of scientific thought, were deeply familiar with the works of previous scholars. There are facts about this, and Bukhara scholars in the 17th century wrote not only about religion and Sharia, but they were also familiar with the teachings of the Peripatetics and Stoics" [9].

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